

The Effect of Solvent Polarity on the Absorption Spectra of Mesoionic 4,5-diphenylisoydnone and 4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole

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Mesoionic compounds were shown^{1,2} to display a blue shift in their characteristic long wave length bands with increasing polarity of the medium; and transition energy (ΔE_T) was fairly linear with respect to Kosower Z -scale³. Further, possibility of utilising the slopes from the plots of ΔE_T vs Z has already been indicated⁴. However, data on other mesoionic compounds are also required, and accordingly, we submit here our preliminary findings with respect to 4,5-diphenylisoydnone (I) and 4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (II).

The required isoydnone (I) was obtained by known^{5,6a} method and the observed properties were in agreement with recorded values, m.p. 165–66° (benzene); $\nu_{C=O}$, 1760 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 267 and 312 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 11,600 and 9,000); reported^{5,6a} m.p. 165–67° and 167°; $\nu_{C=O}$, 1755 and 1763 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 226 and 312 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 11,100 and 8,400). The effect of solvent polarity on the 312 $\text{m}\mu$ band is recorded in Table I.

Preparation of II according to Lazaris⁷ gave only traces of the material, but using an excess of phosphorus oxychloride (2.5 mole), it was obtained in high yield (96%), m.p. 175–76°. As the compound is sensitive to warm alcohol, it was crystallised from cold aqueous IMF (60% recovery) as yellow needles, m.p. 179–80° dec., reported⁷ 170–71°, IR indicate absence of C = O band with $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ at 252 and 342 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 14,900 and 4,100). Reported^{6b} properties of the isomeric mesoionic compound (IV) are as follows : m.p. 176–78°; $\nu_{C=O}$, 1653 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 234 and 335 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ , 13,300 and 6,800). Solvent sensitivity of the 342 $\text{m}\mu$ band (for II) is included in Table I.

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TABLE I

Spectral data on mesoionic compounds (I and II)

Sl. No.	Solvent	Z Kcal/M	I		II	
			λ_{\max} m μ (ϵ)	ΔE_T Kcal/M	λ_{\max} m μ (ϵ)	ΔE_T Kcal/M
1.	Methanol	83.6	307(6,600) 227(10,700)	93.16	333(6,180) -----	85.90
2.	Ethanol—95%	81.2	312(9,000) 227(11,600)	91.66	342(4,100) 252(14,900)	83.64
3.	n-Butanol	77.7	315(9,230) 228(16,880)	90.80	353(5,500) 255(22,400)	81.00
4.	Acetonitrile	71.3	317(9,400) 232(10,590)	90.22	362(6,890) 255(23,900)	79.02
5.	Chloroform	63.2	324(10,100)	88.28	380(6,500)	75.26
6.	Benzene	54.0	336(8,900)	85.13	405(5,770)	70.62

Inspection of the spectral data in Table I clearly demonstrates the sensitivity of the long wave length bands in I and II to solvent polarity. In fact, when the slopes (ΔE_T vs Z) are compared with previous^{1,2} data, the following order is observed :

Other interesting features are stated below. The integrated C = O band intensities^{6a} as well as known dipole moments^{6a} reflect slightly higher polarity of the C = O bond in isosydnes compared to sydnones⁸. The observed higher slope in I compared to 3-phenylsydnone therefore conforms to known properties of isosydnes. The significant difference in slope between I and II is clearly understood in terms of C = S bond in II⁹.

Dipole moment of II is not known, but from the work of Atkin and others⁹ on related mesoionic compounds, it is anticipated to be quite close to that (9.25) of 4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (III). However, the observed slope in II (roughly twice that of III) in conjunction with λ_{\max} and ΔE_T values strongly indicate higher polarity of C = S bond in II compared to III. In other words, between the two mesoionic compounds, II and III, formal negative charge on the *exo*-sulphur is relatively high, and there is less double bond character in C = S bond in the case of II. Data on other mesoionic compounds will be reported in due course.

Spectral data were obtained with Hilger recording spectrophotometer in 1 cm cells at $26 \pm 1^\circ$. Accuracy of the wave length measurement is ± 0.5 m μ . Solvents were purified as before^{2,3}.

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